

Thus with these ratios it can be concluded that tinperoxychromate contains $(Cr_2O_{10})^{-2}$ ion in its constitution.

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References

1. RIESENFELD and COWORKERS, *Ber*, 1905, 38, 4068; *Ber*, 1908, 41, 3941.
2. S. A. RAYNOLD and J. H. REEDY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1851.
3. KLEMON and WERTH, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 216, 127.
4. J. BELTRAN, MARTINEZ and M. REEA, *Anales real Soc. Espan Tias quim*, (Madrid), 1953, 6, 210; 1955, 51, 131.
5. SCHWARZ and GIESE, *Ber.*, 1932, 65B, 871.
6. PRAKASH and PURI, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 94, 275.
7. R. C. RAI, D.Sc. Thesis, Allahabad University, 1962.

Some Dyes as Visual Indicators for Titration of Organic Acids in Alcohol Medium

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TITRATION in alcohol is extensively used in varnish, oil and many other chemical industries for determination of acid value. Generally, phenolphthalein is used as the indicator; it is however far from satisfactory, the colour change being faint and unsharp much unlike that in water medium. Some indicators specially of sulphonaphthalein class have been recommended¹, though hardly ever used. Palit² was the earliest to introduce thymol blue (whose pK is rather unfavourable for normal aqueous titration) in non-aqueous titration; however, its sensitivity is strongly affected by the presence of small quantities of water. In this note we draw attention to the possibility of using some ordinary dyes as indicators which normally do not function as acid-base indicators in aqueous medium.

Experimental

During our studies of electrolysis of dyes in W-tubes in alcoholic solution to produce multiple boundaries³ we noted that quite a few dyes form contrasting colours between the cathodic solution (alkaline) and the anodic solution (acidic), though they do not normally behave as acid-base indicators in water. This is not at all surprising as red form of methylene blue is well-known⁴. Our results for titration of a number of weak organic acids using some such dyes, which are found satisfactory are briefly summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Dyes and indicators	Colour change acid - alkali	Sharpness of colour change in absolute alcohol	
		N/10 acid	N/100 acid
Aniline blue	Red to blue	Extremely sharp	Good
Victoria blue	—do—	—do—	Good
Thionine blue	—do—	Very sharp	Fair
Methylene blue	—do—	Fair	Poor
Thymol blue	Yellow to blue	Extremely sharp	Good

A number of blue dyes whose basic form is red has been found to serve as excellent indicators. Aniline blue and victoria blue are strongly recommended for such titration. The change of colour is very sharp and occurs at the theoretical point. There is no 'blank' and neutral rectified spirit can also be used. For very precise results the titration should be done with exclusion of CO₂, as CO₂ tends to change the red form to blue. The commercial dyes can be used as such. For very precise work the dye should be used after conversion to the red form which can be obtained at the anode on electrolysis of the dye solution in a W-tube^{2,3} (the dye solution in alcohol being charged into the cathode chamber only, the rest being filled with alcohol). Commercial alcohol-soluble resins (such as resin, pale shellac, etc.) and oils, unless too dark, can be successfully titrated with precision.

Thymol blue is almost as good as the dyes mentioned above but tends to give slightly low results. Also, as mentioned earlier, its sensitivity decreases very much in presence of water and so is somewhat unsatisfactory in rectified spirit. Methylene blue is not quite as satisfactory as the aforementioned dyes; however its sensitivity increases if used in its 'red' form obtained either by electrolysis or by benzene extraction⁵.

It is hoped that these dyes should be used in routine industrial determination of acid value of commercial products.

References

1. E. BISHOP, 'Indicators', Pergamon Press, 1972.
2. S. R. PALIT, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 246.
3. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 963.
4. S. R. PALIT, *Nature*, 1944, 153, 317.

A Dye as a Catalyst for Decomposition of Hydrogen Peroxide

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THERE has lately been great revival of interest in the study of the rate of catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ due to its evident relevance to enzyme action. In particular many metal-organic compounds have been